

FIRE RESISTANCE CELLULOSIC FIBERS FOR GREEN POLYMER COMPOSITES

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1 Abstract

Cellulosic fiber polymer composites have received very much attraction for various industrial applications because of their lower density, cost-effectiveness and renewable cellulosic fiber composition. However, the uses of cellulosic fibers in these composites are limited in many applications that require fire resistance due to the flammability and the low thermal resistance of the cellulosic fibers. This paper reports an innovative and sustainable treatment approaches to retard the burning of cellulosic fibers for composite production in which a minimum amount of non-toxic and low cost inorganic chemicals have been used. The fibers can be treated in aqueous solutions either in batch or continuous process using conventional equipments. The cellulosic fibers obtained from this approach become self-extinguished while there is no reduction in fiber strength. The composites produced from the cellulosic fibers treated by this approach become self-extinguished without significant negative impact on the mechanical properties. This will open the door for the use of cellulosic fibers in composites in applications where fire resistance is an important issue, particularly in transportation, aerospace and construction.

2 Introduction

Due to the poor flammability resistance of cellulose materials their use in polymer composites is limited in certain applications. Different flame retardants have been utilized to treat the cellulose materials to overcome this challenge to be used in furniture, textiles or composites. The most commonly used flame retardants for those purposes are based on halogen [1], phosphorous [2-5], boron [4], ammonium [3, 4], graphite [6], alkaline-earth

metallic compounds [7] or mixtures thereof. All the compounds listed above have different drawbacks, such as negative impact on the environment (such as halogen based flame retardants), or be washed off due to their good solubility in water (such as Boron), less effectiveness (such as flame retardants based on phosphorous, graphite or alkaline-earth metallic compounds), etc. None of them has been addressed for composite application. This paper reports an innovative and sustainable treatment approaches to retard the burning of cellulosic fibers for thermoset composite production.

3 Experimentation

2.1 Materials

The cellulosic materials have been tested are shown in Table 1. The chemicals used in this work are summarized in Table 2. Prior treated with the chemical the celluloses were cleaned to remove the impurities and contaminants as much as possible.

Table 1. Description of Cellulose Fibers

Sample	Fiber	Weight (g/m ²)
C1	Flax fabric C 20M-2/2 twill from Moss Composites, Belgium in 2008	149
C2	Flax fabric C 20M-2/2 twill from Moss Composites, Belgium in 2010	149
C3	Flax fabric C10M-8H satin from Moss Composites, Belgium	258
C6	Canada woven flax fabric from JB Martin, Canada	240
C7	Hemp mat 1 supplied by Composites Innovation Centre (CIC), Canada	350

Table 2. Description of Chemicals

Chemicals	Company	Description
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Fisher	-
Ca(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Aldrich	≥ 99%
Ca(OH) ₂	Aldrich	≥ 96%
MgCl ₂	Sigma Life Science	-
MgSO ₄	Sigma-Aldrich	≥ 99.5%
Mg(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	Fluka	≥ 99%
Mg(OH) ₂	Alfa Aesar	95-100.5%
NaOH	Aldrich	≥ 98%
KOH	Sigma-Aldrich	≥ 90%
Al(OH) ₃	Aldrich	Reagent grade, Al ₂ O ₃ : 50-57%
AlCl ₃	Sigma-Aldrich	98%
NH ₄ OH	Sigma-Aldrich	ACS reagent, NH ₃ : 28-30%
BaCl ₂	Fisher	Lab grade
BaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	JTBaker Chemical	100.5%
Ba(OH) ₂	Aldrich	~95%
Clay MMT	Southern Clay Products, Inc	Montmorillonite Cloisite Na™ clay (CEC:92 meq/100 g)
Clay LDH	Akzo-Nobel	Layered Double Hydroxides (LDH)-anionic clay

2.2 Treatment processes

Two different fiber treatment processes were used. In one-step treatment processes (P1), cellulosic fiber was soaked in a prepared solution for a period of time. The fibers were then dried in air then in an oven at 120°C for 2 hours prior to testing.

In the two-step treatment processes (P2) cellulosic fiber was soaked in a first solution for 5 to 300 seconds. The fibers were then removed from the treating medium and allowed to dry in air then dried in an oven at 120°C for 2 hours. The dried fibers were then soaked in a second solution for 5 to 300 seconds. Finally the fibers were dried in air then in an oven at 120°C for 2 hours prior to testing. The loading of chemical treatment was determined based on the difference on the weight of the fiber

before and after treatment. The loading of chemical treatment depends on the type of fiber and the type of chemical used in the treatment. It could be just only few percents of the fiber.

2.2 Composite fabrication

Fibers were dried in an oven at 120°C for about 2 hours to remove humidity before use. Laminate composites were prepared by compression molding with Wabash PC 100-2418-2TM under 100 psi pressures at 80°C for fiber/epoxy composites. The fiber content in the composite was about 40 wt%. The thickness of the composite plaque was about 3 mm.

2.2 Measurements

Horizontal Burning Test (UL 94-HB)

A minimum of five specimens for each sample having width x length (WxL) of 0.5 x 6.0 inch (12.7x152.4 mm) were used. Specimens were held at one end in a horizontal position and tilted at 45° with marks at 1, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0 inch from the free end. A flame was applied to the free end of the specimen for 30 seconds or until the flame front reached the 1 inch mark. If combustion continued, the duration was timed between each 0.5 or 1.0 inch mark. Test was conducted on both, the fibers and the composites. For woven and non woven fibers, a thin metallic wire was inserted into the fiber specimen for supporting purpose.

Tensile Test

Tensile tests on fibers were conducted on a fiber strand disassembled from the fabric. The strands in the longitudinal direction in the fabric were separated from the ones in the orthogonal direction. Tests were carried out for both series separately. The tensile properties of the fiber strand were determined at room temperature and 50% relative humidity on an Instron 5548 micro-tester machine, with crosshead distance of 50 mm and speeds of 120 mm/min. The maximum load at break was recorded for each specimen. A minimum of 10 specimens were tested for each type of sample.

The tensile properties of the composites were determined at room temperature and 50% relative humidity on an Instron 5500R machine, with

crosshead speeds of 5 mm/min according to ASTM 3039-00. A minimum of 5 specimens were tested for each type of sample.

4 Results and discussion

Belgium flax fiber samples C2 were treated with different single component systems as indicated in Table 2 for 120 s using the process P1. Results of the burning tests conducted in accordance with the general procedure described above are also shown in Table 3. It is evident from Table 3 that all of the fibers treated with a single component system, including a barium hydroxide system (C2-1/P1), are not self-extinguished. Fibers treated with NaOH even twice or KOH did not continue to burn but did continue to glow. Fibers treated with NaOH and then washed with water did continue to burn, demonstrating that any fire resistant effect afforded by an alkali metal hydroxide alone can be removed if the fibers get wet.

Table 3. C2 fibers treated with single component solutions using P1

Name	Description	Burning Length (x25.4 mm)				
		1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	4.5
		Burning Time (seconds)				
C2	Untreated	5.4	10.1	15.2	20.1	22.5
C2-1	Ba(OH) ₂	6.1	11.9	17.6	23.3	26.5
C2-2	BaCl ₂	5.0	9.1	13.3	17.5	19.8
C2-3	BaCl ₂ twice	7.3	12.6	17.8	22.4	25.2
C2-4	MgNO ₃	4.8	9.4	14.0	18.1	20.3
C2-5	MgCl ₂	6.1	11.7	18.2	24.6	27
C2-6	MgSO ₄	5.2	9.5	14.0	18.1	19.5
C2-7	Mg(OH) ₂	6.2	10.1	14.6	18.8	20.6
C2-8	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	4.8	8.7	12.6	16.3	18.1
C2-9	CaCl ₂	5.1	9.5	14.3	19.0	21.0
C2-10	KOH	G	G	G	G	G-250
C2-11	NaOH	G	G	G	G	G-250

C2-12	NaOH twice	G	G	G	G	G-280
C2-13	NaOH then washed with water	5.5	10.0	14.5	19.7	22.0
C2-14	AlCl ₃	6.5	12.3	18.4	24.8	27.8
C2-15	Al(OH) ₃	5.3	10.2	14.7	18.6	20.9

Belgium flax fiber samples C2 were treated with bi-component systems containing different magnesium and calcium salts of and hydroxide for 120 s using the process P1. Results of the burning tests conducted in accordance with the general procedure described above are shown in Table 4. It is evident from Table 4 that fibers treated with bi-component systems have retarded the flame but in different extents depending on the typical chemicals used. More specifically, the fibers treated with (MgCl₂+NaOH), (CaCl₂+NaOH), and (AlCl₃+NaOH) are self-extinguishing. Fibers treated with (Mg(NO₃)₂+NaOH) and with (Ca(NO₃)₂+NaOH) did not burn but continued to glow. Fibers treated with (MgSO₄+NaOH) continued to burn, but at a slower rate than untreated fibers. The efficiency of the (MgCl₂+NaOH) system is greater than the (Mg(NO₃)₂+NaOH) system, which is greater than the (MgSO₄+NaOH) system. This is also similar for the calcium-containing systems where the efficiency of the (CaCl₂+NaOH) system is greater than the (Ca(NO₃)₂+NaOH) system. Thus, chloride is the most preferred counter anion for the alkaline earth metal cation.

Table 4. Fibers treated with bi-component systems using P1, P2

Name	Description	Burning Length (x25.4 mm)				
		1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	4.5
		Burning Time (seconds)				
C2	Untreated	5.4	10.1	15.2	20.1	22.5
C2-16	MgCl ₂ +NaOH	14.0	NB	NB	NB	NB
C2-17	Mg(NO ₃) ₂ +NaOH	G	G	G	G	G-180 - 260
C2-18	MgSO ₄ +	10.	19.	29.	38.	43.

	NaOH	6	5	5	7	4
C2-19	CaCl ₂ +NaOH	NB	NB	NB	NB	NB
C2-20	Ca(NO ₃) ₂ +NaOH	G	G	G	G	G 50-300
C2-34/P1	AlCl ₃ +NH ₄ OH	NB	NB	NB	NB	NB
C2-34-Clay/P2	(AlCl ₃ +NH ₄ OH)+clay MMT	NB	NB	NB	NB	NB

Various fiber samples C2, C3, C4, C6 and C7 as described in Table 1 were treated with a magnesium-containing bi-component systems for 120 s using the process P1. Results of the burning tests are shown in Table 5. It is evident from Table 5 that all of the fibers are self-extinguishing after treatment with the (MgCl₂+NaOH)% system. It proves that the treatments are efficient across a range of cellulose materials.

Table 5. Different fibers treated with a Magnesium-containing bi-component systems using P1

Name	Description	Burning Length (x25.4 mm)				
		1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	4.5
		Burning Time (seconds)				
C2	Untreated C2	5.4	10.1	15.2	20.1	22.5
C2-21	C2+ MgCl ₂ +NaOH	14.0	NB	NB	NB	NB
C3	Untreated C3	8.5	15.5	22.9	30.2	34.1
C3-2	C3+ MgCl ₂ +NaOH	G 80-110	NB	NB	NB	NB
C6	Untreated C6	4.8	8.4	12.0	15.6	18.0
C6-2	C6+ MgCl ₂ +NaOH	G 35-215	NB	NB	NB	NB
C7	Untreated C7	5.7	10.0	14.8	19.6	22.6
C7-2	C7+ MgCl ₂ +NaOH	NB	NB	NB	NB	NB

Figure 1 illustrates the remains of the flax fiber after burning. The non-treated flax burned completely to

form the grey ash while the treated flax behaves differently. A formation of the black char after burning for the one treated with Ba(OH)₂ while the fiber becomes self extinguishing after treated with CaCl₂+NaOH.

Tensile properties of untreated Belgium flax fiber samples C2 and of various treated C2 fiber samples were measured in accordance with the procedure described above. Table 6 lists the fiber strands that were tested as well as their tensile properties. The strands in the longitudinal direction in the fabric are denoted as parallel, whereas the ones in the orthogonal direction are denoted as perpendicular.

Figure 1. Fiber specimens after burning test

It is evident from Table 6 that the tensile properties did not change much for most of the systems indicating that treatment did not generally have a detrimental effect on tensile properties. However, for fibers treated with alkali metal hydroxide alone (e.g. KOH and NaOH), there is a significant loss in tensile properties. It is clear, therefore, that cellulose materials treated with both alkaline earth metal salt and alkali metal hydroxide are advantageously fire retardant, often self-extinguishing, while retaining

good tensile properties, in contrast to fibers treated with alkali metal hydroxide or metal salt alone.

Table 6. Tensile strength of tows of treated C2 fibers

Fiber	Description	Tensile Properties Max load (N)	
		Parallel	Perpendicular
C2	Untreated C2	20.4 ± 3.3	23.8 ± 4.1
C2-1/P1	Ba(OH) ₂	21.7 ± 3.2	24.1 ± 4.4
C2-2/P1	BaCl ₂	21.1 ± 3.1	25.1 ± 2.9
C2-4/P1	Mg(NO ₃) ₂	23.8 ± 3.5	25.5 ± 4.7
C2-7/P1	Mg(OH) ₂	19.2 ± 3.4	23.6 ± 2.7
C2-10/P1	KOH	15.8 ± 2.1	20.2 ± 2.9
C2-11/P1	NaOH	15.8 ± 1.4	19.0 ± 2.6
C2-13/P1	NaOH then washed with water	13.2 ± 1.9	18.4 ± 4.8
C2-15/P1	Al(OH) ₃	22.8 ± 1.8	23.6 ± 2.7
C2-17/P1	MgCl ₂ +NaOH	21.3 ± 3.2	23.7 ± 3.2
C2-18/P1	MgSO ₄ +NaOH	23.0 ± 3.6	25.8 ± 3.3
C2-19/P1	CaCl ₂ +NaOH	19.5 ± 3.4	24.9 ± 3.1
C2-20/P1	Ca(NO ₃) ₂ +NaOH	24.4 ± 3.8	24.8 ± 3.9

Horizontal burning tests were conducted in the epoxy-flax fiber composites, the results are shown in Table 7 and the photos of the composites after tested are shown in Figure 2. Burning time represents the amount of time it took for the sample to burn the stated length. Thus, a longer time to burn a given length is an indication of better fire resistance. It is evident from Table 7 that the conventional flax composite is flammable while the fire-resistant flax fibers of this innovation approach have stopped the composites from burning completely.

Mechanical properties of the epoxy-flax fiber composite samples are shown in Table 8. It is evident from Table 8 that epoxy composites containing flax fibers treated in accordance with the present invention have very slightly reduction in tensile strength and modulus than the comparative samples, while improving the energy to break which represents the composite toughness.

Table 7. Burning Test Results of Epoxy/Flax Composites

Sample	Burning length (inches)					
	0.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0
	Burning Time (seconds)					
Epo-C2	0	111	-	-	425	542
Epo-C2-34/P1	0	NB	NB	NB	NB	NB
Epo-C2-34-Clay MMT/P2	0	NB	NB	NB	NB	NB

Table 8. Mechanical Properties of Epoxy/Flax Composites

Sample	Tensile stress (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Energy to break (J)
Epo-C2	117.7 ± 4.0	9.8±0.6	33.7±2.0
Epo-C2-34/P1	106.4 ± 1.0	7.2±0.3	36.7±2.6
Epo-C2-34-Clay MMT/P2	103.7 ± 4.2	8.4±0.2	36.7±2.6

a)

b)

c)

Figure 2. Photos of the epoxy composites with a) untreated and b) treat fiber C2-34/P1and c) treat fiber C2-34-clay MMT/P2

5 Conclusions

Coating of a layer of effective chemicals on the cellulosic fibers significantly improves its fire resistance. The treated cellulosic material becomes self-extinguishing. For epoxy composite, the conventional flax composite is flammable while the treated flax fiber composites have stopped from burning while the mechanical properties are preserved. Thus, this approach allows the production of green composites from cellulosic fibers with improved fire resistance.

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